

Polarographic Study of the Complex Formed by Cadmium with 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane Tetra-acetic Acid

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Reduction of cadmium in CDTA has been studied at an ionic strength of 0.1 at different pHs. Below pH 1.1, complex formation between cadmium and CDTA does not occur. As the pH increases, more and more of cadmium is complexed with the anion of CDTA. Above pH 6.0, Cd^{2+} forms stable complex (1:1) with CDTA. The stability constant of the complex has been calculated by a method devised by Schwarzenbach. The value of K_{MZ} comes to be 19.118 at 30° ($\mu=0.1$). As the ionic strength increases, stability constant decreases, showing that the complex is less stable at higher ionic strength.

The complexes of 1,2-diaminocyclohexane tetra-acetic acid (CDTA) are for the most part considerably more stable than those of ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA)¹. Pribil *et al.*² proposed CDTA for use in complexometric titrations. The stability constants of many metal ions with CDTA have been determined by Schwarzenbach and co-workers¹ by pH and potentiometric measurements. We have studied the polarography of the complex formed by CDTA with lanthanum, europium, ytterbium³, and lead⁴. The present communication describes the polarographic study on the complex formed by CDTA with cadmium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Weighed amount of A. R. grade cadmium nitrate was dissolved in conductivity water and estimated as usual. 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane tetra-acetic acid, supplied by L. Light & Co., was used as such without further purification. Solution of its disodium salt (Na_2Z) was prepared and stored in polyethylene bottle. pH of the solution was adjusted by adding perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide solution. Potassium nitrate was added to keep constant ionic strength. During amperometric titrations, buffers of different pHs were used.

Polarographic measurements were carried out in the same way as described in the preceding communication.⁴

Since the reduction of the complex was found to be an irreversible process, the stability of the complex was determined by a method suggested by Schwarzenbach and co-workers¹ which involves the determination of free copper in presence of its complex polarographically.

1. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, **37**, 937.
2. *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1953, **18**, 43.
3. Jain and Gaur, paper presented at the IIIrd International Congress of Polarography held at Southampton (U. K.) 19th-25th July, 1964.
4. *Idem*, this issue, p. 753.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4196.

The equilibrium constant (K) of the reaction:

is given by the expression (I) if we take equimolar quantities of CuZ^{2-} and Cd^{2+} .

$$K = \frac{(\% \text{Cu})^2}{(100 - \% \text{Cu})^2} \quad \dots \text{(I)}$$

Knowing the percentage of the uncomplexed copper in the mixture, K can be calculated. The stability constant K_{Mz} of the cadmium complex is given by

$$K = \frac{K_{Mz}}{K_{CuZ}} \text{ or } K_{Mz} = K \cdot K_{CuZ} \quad \dots \text{(II)}$$

The value of K_{CuZ} , as reported by Schwarzenbach, is $10^{21.3}$, so K_{Mz} can be calculated.

A mixture containing copper-CDTA complex ($0.001M$), $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ ($0.001M$), sodium acetate ($0.01M$), and acetic acid ($0.01M$) was prepared. Potassium nitrate was added to keep a constant ionic strength (0.1). Subsequent procedure is same as described earlier.⁴

Polarographic Study.—Solutions containing 1 mM of Cd^{2+} , 2 mM of CDTA (Na_3Z) in $0.1M$ potassium nitrate were polarographed. At pH 0.9 and 1.10 , single reduction wave occurred having a half-wave potential at -0.574 V . At pH 1.26 , two reduction waves appeared; the half-wave potential of the 1st wave was at -0.57 V vs. S. C. E., whereas the second wave had half-wave potential at -0.96 S V vs. S. C. E. As the pH of the solution increased beyond 1.26 , the height of the first wave decreased and that of the second wave increased. The half-wave potential of the first wave remained at -0.57 V vs. S. C. E., whereas that of the second wave shifted towards the more negative side. Above pH 2.1 , the first wave disappeared showing only one reduction wave; half-wave potential of the second wave shifted towards the more negative side with the increase of pH . Above pH 3.5 , the reduction wave, however, combined with the wave due to hydrogen and hence measurements could not be extended. At pH greater than 5.0 , no reduction wave appeared before the decomposition of the supporting electrolyte (Fig. 1). The first reduction wave is due to free Cd^{2+} , whereas the second wave is for the reduction of Cd-CDTA complex. The plot of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ for Cd-CDTA complex wave was found to be linear, but the slope of the line had much higher value than that required for two-electron reversible reduction. Temperature coefficient of i_d was found to be of the order of 1.1% . Results are recorded in Table I.

FIG. 1. Polarograms of $1mM \text{ Cd}^{2+} + 2mM \text{ CDTA}$ in $0.1M\text{-KNO}_3$ at different pH .
(a) 0.9 , (b) 1.1 , (c) 1.2 , (d) 1.6 , (e) 2.06 , (f) 2.5 , (g) 2.92 , (h) 3.42 , (i) 4.3 ,

Composition of the Complex

Amperometric Titrations.—Amperometric titrations of solutions containing the same amount of Cd^{2+} (at different pH) with CDTA (Na_2Z) were carried out. Results of the direct titrations are recorded in Table II.

Below pH 6.0, the ratio of $\text{Cd}^{2+}:\text{Na}_2\text{Z}$ was found to be less than 1.0, but at higher pH (7-10), it was 1:1. Reverse titrations were also carried out at pH range of 7-10 and the ratio was found to be 1:1. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE I
 Cd^{2+} conc. = 1.0mM. Na_2Z conc. = 2.0mM.

pH of the soln.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (-V vs. S.C.E.).	i_d .	Temp. coeff. of i_d .	Slope.
0.90	0.574 V	40 mm		
1.10	0.573	38		
1.26	I wave 0.570	25		
	II 0.968	21	1.00%	0.098 V
1.60	I 0.517	8		0.032
	II 1.010	32	1.13	0.096
2.06	I 0.570	3		
	II 1.014	35	1.10	0.108
2.50	I			
	II 1.084	38		0.108
2.92	1.174			
3.42	1.540			
4.30	1.680			

TABLE II
Direct titration of Cd^{2+} with CDTA (Na_2Z).
 Cd^{2+} soln. = 20.0 ml.

pH of the soln.	Conc. ratio.		Na_2Z soln. reqd.	Ratio at equiv. point.	Applied voltage, (V vs. S.C.E.)
	Cd^{2+} .	Na_2Z .			
2.0	0.001M	0.01M	1.82 ml	1:0.91	-0.65
3.0	0.001	0.01	1.65	1:0.82	-0.63
5.0	0.001	0.01	1.70	1:0.85	-0.65
6.0	0.001	0.01	1.98	1:0.99	-0.70
7.0	0.001	0.01	2.00	1:1.0	-0.75
8.0	0.001	0.01	2.00	1:1.0	-0.80
10.0	0.001	0.01	2.03	1:1.01	-0.90

N.B. Complex formed in all cases was CdZ^{2-}

TABLE III
Reverse titration of cadmium with CDTA (Na_2Z).
 Na_2Z soln. = 5.0 ml.

pH of the soln.	Conc. ratio.		$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. required.	Ratio at equiv. point ($\text{Cd}^{2+}:\text{CDTA}$).	Applied voltage (V vs. S.C.E.).
	Cd^{2+} .	Na_2Z .			
7.0	0.025M	0.01M	1.99	0.995:1	-0.75
10.0	0.025	0.01	1.97	0.985:1	-0.90

N.B. Complex formed was CdZ^{2-} .

Stability Constant of the Complex

The stability constant of the Cd-CDTA complex have been calculated as described previously. The results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

μ .	Temp.	%Free Cd^{2+} .	Log K_{MZ} .	$K_{MZ} \times 10^{16}$.
0.1	30°	7.50	19.117	1.31
1.0	30°	5.71	18.865	0.732

DISCUSSION

From the polarograms at different pHs, it is evident that below pH 1.1, Cd^{2+} forms no complex with the anion of CDTA. As the pH increases above 1.1, complex formation occurs between Cd^{2+} and the anion of CDTA, which is shown by two reduction waves. As the pH increases, more and more of Cd^{2+} is complexed. Above pH 4.5, the complex is nonreducible. Below pH 6, the complex is not stable since the ratio of Cd^{2+} : Na_2Z , as determined by the amperometric titrations, has been found to be less than 1. The stable complex in the ratio of 1:1 is formed above pH 6.0. Reduction of the complex is an irreversible process and hence the stability constant could not be calculated by measuring shift in half-wave potential⁶. A method devised by Schwarzenbach⁷ provides the value of log K_{MZ} as 19.118 at 30° ($\mu = 0.1$). At $\mu = 1.0$ ($t = 30^\circ$). This value changes to 18.865 which shows that the stability of the complex decreases with the increasing ionic strength. The value obtained by the above method is in agreement with the value reported by Schwarzenbach⁷. The stability constant of Cd-CDTA complex is nearly two-order higher in magnitude than that of the Cd-EDTA complex. The difference may be due to the structural rigidity between the two nitrogen atoms imparted by the presence of the cyclohexyl ring in 1,2-diamino-cyclohexane tetra-acetic acid.

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6. I. M. Kolthoff and J. J. Lingane, "Polarography", Interscience publication, Vol. I (2nd ed.), 1952, p. 214.